

CLINICAL ARTICLE

Agreement between the short and long versions of the Resilience Scale: A validation among the obstetric population according to vulnerability status

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Keywords

pregnancy, pregnancy complications, resilience, scale, vulnerability

Synopsis

1 The current findings suggest that the short version of the Resilience Scale (RS-14) may not
2 be a suitable replacement for the original version (RS-25) in obstetrics.
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7 **Abstract**

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9 **Objective:** To compare the 14-item Resilience Scale (RS-14) and the original 25-item scale
10 (RS-25) in the obstetric population, including vulnerable and non-vulnerable women.
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13 **Methods:** A Brazilian prospective cohort study was conducted of nulliparous singleton
14 pregnant women from March 2018 to March 2020. Women who completed the RS-25 at 27–
15 29 weeks of pregnancy were included in the analysis. RS-25 and RS-14 scores were
16 converted to comparable scales of 0–100. Medians, standard deviations, and centiles
17 between versions were compared for the general, vulnerable, and non-vulnerable
18 populations. Correlation, concordance, and internal consistency and reliability analyses were
19 performed. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.
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31 **Results:** In total, 381 women who completed the RS-25 were included. Medians of RS-14
32 and RS-25 scores were significantly different (73.4 and 70.8, respectively; $p < 0.001$),
33 regardless of the vulnerability status. The RS-14 showed a high correlation (Pearson's
34 correlation coefficient of -0.379 (p -value < 0.001), but no agreement (Pitman's test of
35 difference in variance: $r = 0.422$; $P < 0.001$) with the RS-25 version. RS-14 showed high
36 internal consistency and reliability with only one component (Variance of 59.82%,
37 Cronbach's Alpha 0.947).
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48 **Conclusion:** The RS-14 may overestimate the RS-25 score and different domains may not
49 be assessed by the short version. The psychometric properties of the RS-14 and the clinical
50 relevance of the variation between versions require further evaluation.
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58 **1 INTRODUCTION**

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1 In the face of adversity, individuals may react to difficult situations differently, which can
2 range from succumbing to overcoming. Resilience is the personal resource for coping with
3 difficulties [1, 2]. During pregnancy, a woman may experience resilience according to her
4 social position, psychological resources, interpersonal relationships, and other
5 biopsychosocial characteristics [3].
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10 WHO promotes an approach to maternal care that goes beyond the prevention of pregnancy
11 complications and focuses on achieving a positive experience during pregnancy and
12 childbirth [4, 5]. For this purpose, WHO developed tools to improve the multidimensional
13 measurement of maternal health including individual and social factors, and access to health
14 services [6, 7].
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24 The Wagnild & Young Resilience Scale (RS-25), published in 1993, is one of the main
25 instruments used to measure this capacity [8, 9]. It was developed in 1987 with 24 North
26 American women who were selected due to overcoming serious adversities in life [8]. The
27 scale was developed to identify degrees of individual resilience, including dimensions such
28 as personal competence, acceptance of herself, and acceptance of life. These dimensions
29 reflect positive psychosocial adaptations to cope with adverse situations [8, 9]. The scale is
30 composed of 25 items with Likert-type responses, ranging from “totally disagree” (1 point) to
31 “totally agree” (7 points). In 2009, the same authors shortened and validated the initial 25-
32 item version to a 14-item scale (RS-14). The RS-14 demonstrated good internal consistency
33 and adequate psychometric properties (Cronbach’s alpha coefficient 0.93) and has been
34 used in recent years [10, 11]. In 2005, Pesce et al. [12] transculturally validated and adapted
35 the scale to Brazilian Portuguese using seventh- and eighth-grade middle school students
36 and first- and second-year high school students in Rio de Janeiro. The Brazilian Portuguese
37 version showed a good internal consistency (Cronbach’s alpha 0.80).
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1 A comprehensive approach may require a great number of instruments, which may make
2 the evaluation of the women's well-being challenging [13–15]. The validation of shorter
3 instruments is important, therefore, to facilitate the multidimensional assessment during
4 antenatal care visits. Both the RS-25 and RS-14 scales have been validated and translated
5 into Brazilian Portuguese. These scales were transculturally adapted and also applied to the
6 obstetric population [10, 11, 16]. According to Wagnild [17], the average time for applying
7 the original scale was 5–7 minutes and the time decreased by half when the short version
8 (RS-14) was used.

9 The aim of the present study was to compare and validate the short version of the resilience
10 scale (RS-14) using the original 25-item scale (RS-25) as reference, in a population of
11 nulliparous pregnant women (with and without maternal vulnerability).

12 **2 METHODS**

13 **Study design and participants**

14 The Maternal Actigraphy Exploratory Study I (MAES-I) project is a prospective cohort study
15 that included nulliparous singleton pregnant women from mid-pregnancy to childbirth in four
16 Brazilian centers from March 2018 to March 2020. The study protocol has been previously
17 published [18]. Briefly, the study was designed to explore predictors of gestational
18 complications, including clinical conditions and patterns of physical activity and sleep, based
19 on actigraphy data by means of a wearable wrist actigraphy device used 24 hours/day
20 uninterrupted, from 19 to 21 weeks until childbirth. Singleton pregnant women were
21 considered eligible until 21 weeks of pregnancy. Exclusion criteria are described in Table S1
22 (Supplementary Material) and include a history of repeat abortions, confirmed fetal
23 malformation, chronic arterial hypertension with the use of anti-hypertensives before
24 pregnancy, moderate/severe hypertension (>160/100 mm Hg) on admission to the study,

1 diagnosis of diabetes before pregnancy, uterine malformation: bicornuate uterus or uterine
2 septum, history of uterine cerclage, thyroid disease, current use of medication, and use of
3 anti-depressants/anxiolytic agents, among others. Sample calculation was based on the
4 prevalence of a composite outcome, dependent on the main adverse obstetric outcomes
5 (gestational diabetes mellitus, pre-eclampsia, bleeding complications, etc.), resulting in a
6 minimal number of 384 women for inclusion in the cohort.
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13 **Procedures**

14 Follow-up of each participant occurred from the time of inclusion into the study to childbirth
15 at three visits (at 19–21 weeks, 27–29 weeks, 37–39 weeks, and postpartum before
16 discharge). Sociodemographic data, history of maternal health, and pregnancy outcomes
17 were collected during study visits. Pregnancy and childbirth outcomes were analyzed on
18 medical chart review.
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28 **Resilience Scale and vulnerability**

29 The Resilience Scale was applied during the visit at 27–29 weeks. The participant was
30 instructed on completing the scale in a dedicated room. The research assistant reviewed
31 completion of the scale to confirm whether any questions had been left unanswered.
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38 Subsequently, data were entered into the electronic database system. The present study
39 used the Portuguese version of the Wagnild & Young Resilience Scale (RS-25) (1993) [8],
40 translated by Pesce et al. [12], which was applied during the second visit.
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46 Both the RS-25 [8] and RS-14 [10, 11] versions are composed of questions with Likert-type
47 responses rated on a scale of 1–7 points, according to the level of agreement (Table 1). It
48 ranged from “totally disagree” (minimum score of 1) to “totally agree” (maximum score of 7).
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53 Resilience scores according to the original (RS-25) and short version (RS-14) were
54 calculated by the sum of the responses to each question, in the range of 25–175 and 14–98
55 scores, respectively. Resilience can also be classified as low, moderate, and high (Table 1)
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1 [10, 11]. Both versions of the scale can be divided into five domains for the assessment of
2 resilience, including self-reliance, meaningfulness, equanimity, perseverance, and existential
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5 aloneness (Table 1).
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7 Later, the scores of both scales were converted into a “relative score” version, in which both
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9 scores were in the range of 0–100. For this, scores of the long and short versions were
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11 submitted to the following equations: $(RS-25)*100/175$ and $(RS-14)*100/98$. This
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13 proportional conversion allowed for the comparison between different versions of the
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16 resilience scales.
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19 Information was collected on aspects related to maternal vulnerability, defined as one of the
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21 following conditions: low family income (less than 1000 Brazilian Reais per month); lack of a
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23 partner (single, widow, divorced); adolescent (age under 19 years); and low level of
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25 education (less than 8 years). Similarly, women without any previous criteria were classified
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27 as not being vulnerable.
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31 **Statistical analysis**

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33 Data extracted from the online database were processed and analyzed using SPSS version
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35 20 software (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). To compare the scores between the RS-14 and RS-
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37 25 versions, medians (and standard deviations) and percentiles were used. Differences in
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39 medians were tested by related samples, using the Wilcoxon signed rank test. A linear
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41 correlation between the short and original versions was analyzed using Pearson’s
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43 correlation coefficient. Agreement between the RS-14 and RS-25 scores was assessed
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45 using the Bland–Altman plot to analyze the mean and variance of the difference between
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47 scores, and the Pitman test of difference in variance. $P<0.05$ was considered statistically
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49 significant. Finally, to evaluate internal consistency of the RS-14 instrument, a confirmatory
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51 factor analysis (CFA) was performed, using the Generalized Least Squares method,
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1 Varimax rotation with Kaiser Normalization, and Cronbach's alpha coefficient. An Eigenvalue
2 greater than 1 was used to retain the number of factors.
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4 **Ethics**

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7 The MAES-I study was approved by the National Research Ethics Committee in Brazil
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9 (CONEP) and by the institutional review board of the coordinating center (Letter of approval
10 1.834.116, issued on November 24, 2016) and all other Brazilian participating centers. An
11 invitation was extended to all women considered eligible for this study, and all provided
12 informed consent to participate. Methodological procedures and ethical aspects of the
13 present study were in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki, amended in Hong Kong in
14 1989, and Brazilian ethical principles of the Brazilian National Health Council (Resolution
15 CNS 466/12). Methodological and ethical aspects of the study also followed the STROBE
16 guidelines [19].
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31 **3 RESULTS**

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34 Of the 400 women originally included in the MAES-I study, 381 women completed the 25-
35 item Resilience Scale during the 27-29 weeks visit (Figure S1). Sixty-eight women did not
36 have any criterion of vulnerability and 313 had at least one criterion of vulnerability (Table 2).
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38 The distributions of the RS-14 and RS-25 scores were significantly different, regardless of
39 the status of vulnerability shown by these women (Figure 1). Medians were 73.4 and 70.8
40 ($p < 0.001$), respectively (Table 2). The 50th (median), 75th, 90th and 95th centiles were
41 significantly different between both versions of the resilience scale (Table 2). RS-14 scores
42 had statistically significant higher values than RS-25 scores for these centiles. Resilience
43 scores differed between women with and without vulnerability, regardless of the version of
44 resilience scale (Table 2). Vulnerable women had lower medians of resilience scores
45 according to RS-14 (82.1 vs 69.3, $p < 0.001$) and RS-25 (78.8 vs 67.7, $p < 0.001$) (Table 2).
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1 Figure 2 shows that the RS-14 and RS-25 versions had strongly correlated scores
2 (Pearson's coefficient of -0.379 (p-value<0.001)). However, Bland-Altman (Figure 3)
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4 showed an asymmetric distribution of the difference in mean scores between scales (Pitman
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6 test of difference in variance $r=0.422$, p-value<0.001). These results demonstrate that there
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8 was no agreement between the scales, and the RS-14 scale seems to overestimate the
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10 values of resilience, when compared to the RS-25.
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13 Confirmatory factorial analysis showed that only one component obtained an Eigenvalue
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15 that was greater than 1 for the RS-14, with a variance of 59.82%. Cronbach's alpha of this
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17 version of the scale was 0.947, showing a high reliability and internal consistency. The
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19 correlation between individual scores from each item ranged from 0.305 to 0.634 (Table S2),
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21 and question 3 of the RS-14 is the only one with a correlation <0.500 (0.305). Question 3 of
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23 the RS-14 was also the only one that caused an increase in Cronbach's alpha of the
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25 instrument when deleted (Table S3).
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31 **4 DISCUSSION**

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33 The findings of the present study suggest that the short version of the Resilience Scale (RS-
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35 14) is not a suitable replacement for the original version (RS-25) in the obstetric population
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37 since there was poor agreement between versions. If used in this population, caution should
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39 be exercised as the short version (RS-14) seems to provide only an overall analysis of
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41 resilience and overestimate it.
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46 Concerning psychometric properties, the present study showed that there was high internal
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48 consistency (degree of reliability) of the short version in this population (Cronbach's alpha
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50 0.947). Reliability was higher than that obtained by Wagnild and Young in 1993 (Cronbach's
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52 alpha 0.91) (19), Damasio et al. in 2011 (Cronbach's alpha 0.82) (26), and Pinheiro and
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54 Matos in 2013 (Cronbach's alpha 0.945) (30). Although there was a high general internal
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56 consistency for the instrument, there are indications that the instrument might benefit from
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modifications related to the exclusion of certain items. In 2011, Damasio et al. analyzed the
psychometric properties of the Brazilian version of the RS-14 in a sample of 1139 individuals
aged 14–59 years [16]. The authors demonstrated that when item 3 was excluded, the
resiliency scale had better goodness-of-fit indexes and internal consistency (Cronbach's
alpha 0.83). In addition, the authors validated the proposed 13-item scale (Brazilian 13-
item), comparing resilience with other aspects that are associated with resilient responses,
including “meaning in life,” using the 12-Item Purpose-in-Life Test (PILTest-12), and
“depression” and “self-efficacy,” using the General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12) [16]. The
RS-13 correlated positively with “meaning in life” and “self-efficacy” and correlated
negatively with “depression,” which was considered intuitive and expected. In the present
study, while all other items of the scale had a correlation greater than 0.500 between them,
item 3 showed a correlation of 0.305. Furthermore, exclusion of this item was the only one
that elevated Cronbach's alpha of the instrument. In this context, exclusion of item 3 should
be considered.

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In the original study that developed the scale, resilience has been defined as a
multidimensional phenomenon [8]. In addition, resilience could be assessed by factors that
encompass the construction of the process of resilience [8]: equanimity, perseverance, self-
reliance, meaningfulness, and existential aloneness. Nevertheless, confirmatory factorial
analysis has shown discordant results, indicating the existence of only two main factors:
“Personal Competence” and “Acceptance of Self and Life.” Both factors explained 44% of
the variance in the construct. In 2009, Wagnild [10] explored a new version of the scale,
aimed at assessing a shorter version with good reliability and that could address the initially
proposed multiple domains. The RS-14 showed an excellent correlation with the RS-25
($r=0.97$) and internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha 0.93) [10, 11]. However, further
analyses indicated a unifactorial solution, responsible for 53% of total variance [11].

1 Similarly, the results of the present study demonstrated that only one factor resulted from
2 confirmatory factorial analysis, which indicates that the short version should be reserved for
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4 the global analysis of resilience, precluding the evaluation per domain. In general, it was
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6 observed that validation of the short version of the instrument, particularly addressing the
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8 domains of resilience, may vary in different studies and populations, requiring further
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10 specific exploration [10–12, 16].
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13 The present study has strengths and limitations that need to be acknowledged. This is one
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15 of the first studies applying the different versions of the Resilience Scale in an obstetric
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17 population. The need to evaluate the scale in different periods of life is highlighted, in view of
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19 the dynamic concept of resilience [20, 21]. The instrument was applied by different
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21 examiners, in different centers, with self-administered questionnaires for pregnant women
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23 during the same period of pregnancy (27–29 weeks). In addition, factors of social
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25 vulnerability were taken into account in the concordance analysis. Resilience may result
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27 from the combination of individual and social contexts, including family and socioeconomic
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29 cultural environments, providing an individual with a dynamic process to overcome adverse
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31 situations [22, 23]. Different degrees of vulnerability may act as a protective or risk factor for
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33 the individual and their ability to cope [23]. Therefore, addressing resilience according to
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35 vulnerability status may confer a more contextual analysis to the construct, which is in
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37 agreement with the concept of resilience.
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46 Despite the relevance of the present study, there are some limitations. The study sample
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48 only included low-risk pregnant women. It is known that resilience encompasses the ability
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50 to overcome adversities. A low-risk population may result in decreased incidence of
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52 pregnancy complications [24]. It is important that further studies be conducted to confirm the
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54 findings in a more diversified and representative sample of Brazilian pregnant women.
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58 Another aspect regarding the profile of the study population was that it included only
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1 nulliparous women. The majority of these women were facing pregnancy/maternity for the
2 first time. It is necessary to evaluate women in other contexts, which may also include
3 women who have had previous experience of motherhood, since it may offer a different
4 perspective on resilience. The present study did not assess other important information on
5 mental health, for example, depression, anxiety, or other mood disorders. These
6 components are associated with resilience [25] and may add to the evaluation of the
7 construct, conferring a more complete approach to global (and mental) health and its
8 relationship with variation in resilience.
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10 The results of the present study indicated that there is a probable need to adjust the
11 instrument for the assessment of resilience in the obstetric population. The exclusion of item
12 3 of the RS-14 has been corroborated by other authors [16], and could potentially contribute
13 to the improvement of the instrument. Further studies are required to evaluate reproducibility
14 of the instrument in pregnant women, since the short scale (RS-14) did not agree with the
15 original scale (RS-25). Assessment of the performance of the short version that classifies
16 women into a low, moderate, and high category of resilience may aid in the evaluation of the
17 applicability of the RS-14 version. Furthermore, a short version of the instrument could be
18 applied in clinical practice for the multidimensional evaluation of women's health, since there
19 are several other important components to be part of the evaluation, including mental health
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48 **Author contributions**

49 JGC and JPS conceived and planned the cohort. JGC, RTS, DFL, FEF, EARF, RBG, JM,
50 MLC, RPT, DSS, KGF, MJM, and AAC developed, implemented, and carried out all related
51 procedures. RTS, AAC, and JGC designed and performed the current analysis. AAC wrote
52 the first draft manuscript under the supervision of RTS and JGC. All authors, including those
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1 from the MAES-I study group, read, reviewed, and approved the final version of the
2 manuscript.
3

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44 **Availability of data and material**

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The dataset used and analyzed during the present study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

51 **Conflicts of interest**

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The authors have no conflicts of interest.

58 **References**

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43 **Figure Legends**

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46 **Figure 1.** Box plot of total scores of the 25-item and 14-item Resilience Scales (RS) for all
47 women and for women with and without vulnerability criteria in the MAES-I study (n=381).
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51 **Figure 2.** Correlation between the 25-item and 14-item Resilience Scale (RS).
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53 Legend: Pearson's correlation coefficient 0.984, $P < 0.001$ (n=381).
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56 **Figure 3.** Bland–Altman comparison of the 25-item and 14-item Resilience Scales.
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Legend: Limits of agreement (reference range for difference): -8.17 to 5.23; mean
difference: -1.47 (SD=3.41). Pitman test of difference in variance: $r=0.420$; $P<0.001$ ($n=381$).

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Table 1. Characteristics of the short and long versions of the resilience scales.

Characteristics	RS-14	RS-25
Range	14–98	25–175
High resilience	>81	>145
Moderate resilience	65–81	125–145
Low resilience	<65	<125
<i>Questions</i>		
I usually manage one way or another	Q1	Q2
I feel proud that I have accomplished things in life	Q2	Q6
I usually take things in stride	Q3	Q7
I am friends with myself	Q4	Q8
I feel that I can handle many things at a time	Q5	Q9
I am determined	Q6	Q10
I can get through difficult times because I've experienced difficulty before	Q7	Q13
I have self-discipline	Q8	Q14
I keep interested in things	Q9	Q15
I can usually find something to laugh about	Q10	Q16
My belief in myself gets me through hard times	Q11	Q17
In an emergency, I'm someone people can generally rely on	Q12	Q18
My life has meaning	Q13	Q21
When I'm in a difficult situation, I can usually find my way out of it	Q14	Q23
<i>Domains</i>		
Self-reliance	Q1, Q5, Q7, Q12, and Q14	Q3, Q7, Q9, Q22, Q23, and Q24
Meaningfulness	Q2, Q9, and Q13	Q6, Q8, Q15, Q16, and Q20
Equanimity	Q3 and Q10	Q1, Q2, Q5, Q12, Q13, Q17, and Q18
Perseverance	Q6 and Q8	Q4, Q10, Q14, and Q19
Existential aloneness	Q4 and Q11	Q11 and Q21

Table 2. Reliability of the 14-item and 25-item Brazilian Portuguese version of the Resilience Scale, including women with (n=313) and without (n=68) vulnerability criteria.

	14-item Resilience Scale	25-item Resilience Scale	P value
<i>Overall</i>			<0.001*
Mean±SD	69.2±18.2	67.7±16.8	
Median	73.4	70.8	
<i>Percentile 5</i>			
No vulnerability	44.8	43.9	
Vulnerable	35.6	34.8	
Total	36.9	37.8	
<i>Percentile 10</i>			
No vulnerability	55.9	51.2	
Vulnerable	42.8	42.3	
Total	43.8	44.0	
<i>Percentile 25</i>			
No vulnerability	73.7	71.2	
Vulnerable	53.0	54.1	
Total	55.1	56.0	
<i>Percentile 50</i>			
No vulnerability	82.1	78.8	
Vulnerable	69.3	67.7	
Total	73.4	70.8	
<i>Percentile 75</i>			
No vulnerability	87.7	84.4	
Vulnerable	83.6	81.1	
Total	84.7	81.7	
<i>Percentile 90</i>			
No vulnerability	89.8	86.8	
Vulnerable	91.9	88.6	
Total	89.8	86.8	

Percentile 95

No vulnerability	93.8	90.3
Vulnerable	93.8	89.1
Total	93.8	89.1

*Related samples Wilcoxon signed rank test. Values in bold were considered statistically significant.

TABLE 3. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) of the Portuguese version of the 14-item Resilience Scale

Questions and domains	Factor
	1
Self-reliance	
Q1. I usually manage one way or another	0.720
Q5. I feel that I can handle many things at a time	0.721
Q7. I can get through difficult times because I've experienced difficulty before	0.727
Q12. In an emergency, I'm someone people can generally rely on	0.830
Q14. When I'm in a difficult situation, I can usually find my way out of it	0.778
Meaningfulness	
Q2. I feel proud that I have accomplished things in life	0.795
Q9. I keep interested in things	0.830
Q13. My life has meaning	0.843
Equanimity	
Q3. I usually take things in stride	0.444
Q10. I can usually find something to laugh about	0.821
Perseverance	
Q6. I am determined	0.850
Q8. I have self-discipline	0.753
Existential aloneness	
Q4. I am friends with myself	0.826

1	Q11. My belief in myself gets me through hard times	0.801
2	Explained Variance, %	59.82
3		
4	Eigenvalue	8.37
5		
6	Cronbach's alpha	0.947
7	<hr/>	
8	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin of 0.958; Bartlett's test $P < 0.001$.	
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Synopsis

Our findings suggest that the short version of the Resilience Scale (RS-14) may not be suitable replacement for the original version (RS-25) in the obstetric.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

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Supplementary File

1251_Supplementary files.docx

